

IMMUNE STATUS INDICATORS IN THE TREATMENT OF ORAL LEUCOPLAKIA

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Abstract: The aim of the work was a comprehensive study of the clinical efficacy and changes in the local immune response during conservative rehabilitation after surgical treatment of leukoplakia of the oral mucosa using local keratoplasty. The dynamics of subjective complaints, clinical manifestations, as well as immune status indicators were assessed: the level of secretory IgA, IL-1 β , IL-6 and TNF- α . The data obtained indicate a pronounced regenerative, antiseptic and immunomodulatory effect of the drug, which confirms its high clinical value in this pathology.

The study included 40 patients (20 men and 20 women) aged 35 to 65 years with clinically and histologically confirmed diagnosis of leukoplakia. Inclusion criteria: presence of leukoplakia foci on the mucous membrane of the cheeks, tongue, and floor of the mouth. Patients after surgical treatment of leukoplakia of the oral mucosa were prescribed KIN Care gel for topical application 2 times a day after oral sanitation for 28 days.

By the 14th day of treatment, patients in the main group showed an increase in sIgA concentration from an average of 0.19 ± 0.05 g/l to 0.31 ± 0.06 g/l ($p < 0.01$), while in the control group the increase was only 0.04 g/l ($p > 0.05$).

Concentration of proinflammatory cytokines:

The level of IL-1 β decreased from 122 ± 13 pg/ml to 68 ± 10 pg/ml ($p < 0.01$), IL-6 – from 96 ± 8 to 49 ± 7 pg/ml ($p < 0.01$), TNF- α – from 75 ± 9 to 40 ± 6 pg/ml ($p < 0.01$).

Discussion. The obtained results confirm the data of other authors on the high regenerative activity of KIN Care gel I. Its ability to stimulate metabolic processes and promote epithelialization makes it an effective drug in the treatment of precancerous conditions of the mucous membrane. An important advantage is the absence of systemic action and high biocompatibility.

The results of the study confirm the immunomodulatory effect of KIN Care gel I. An increase in the level of secretory IgA, along with a decrease in the

concentration of proinflammatory cytokines, indicates stabilization of the local immune status of the mucous membrane. This effect is explained by the action of hyaluronic acid and chlorhexidine [6,8].

Conclusion

The use of KIN Care gel in the complex therapy of leukoplakia of the oral mucosa allows achieving significant clinical improvement with minimal side effects. The drug can be considered as an effective and safe means of local action in this pathology.

Application of KIN Care gel in the treatment of oral leukoplakia helps to normalize the local immune response, reduce inflammation and improve the clinical picture. It is recommended to include the drug in the complex therapy of this pathology.